

Organic farming in mountainous areas: advantages and disadvantages for soil health

Organic farming in mountainous environments constitutes a strategic approach to soil management, aiming to protect biodiversity and enhance the sustainability of crops. In Evrytania, these practices are adapted to the region's specific conditions, such as its mountainous terrain, dense forests and meadows.

Benefits and Challenges of Organic Farming for Mountain Soils

In Evrytania, the main organic farming practices include crop rotation, the use of organic fertilizers such as compost, the avoidance of synthetic pesticides and fertilizers, and the use of cover crops and intercropping. These practices provide significant benefits for soil health, including improved soil structure, increased water and nutrient retention, enhanced biodiversity and nutrient recycling. Furthermore, the limited use of mechanical interventions reduces erosion and strengthens the stability of mountain soil systems. However, the addition of organic farming in mountainous soils also presents challenges. Steep slopes, low natural soil fertility, the need for increased manual labor, and extreme weather conditions can lead to nutrient loss, reduced productivity, and higher production costs.

Figure 1. Organic farming, Klafsi community at the foothills of Mount Koniskos (Municipality of Karpenisi, Evrytania) (Photo: Galanopoulou S., 2025)

Additional Information

The implementation of organic practices in Evrytania contributes to the protection of soil health, the maintenance of biodiversity, and the conservation of water resources. At the same time, due to the lack of large arable areas, the limited growing season, extreme climatic conditions, and steep slopes, careful management and increased effort are required to ensure the long-term sustainability of the crops.

KEYWORDS

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